

LAWS, PRINCIPLES, FUNCTIONS AND METHODS OF MANAGEMENT.

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Amirova Dilshoda Hasan qizi

*Termez is a student of the Institute
of Agrotechnology and Innovative Development*

Management is based on a system of social laws. No major practical problem can be solved without understanding and justifying it theoretically. Theory is an important method of renewal. Science, on the other hand, focuses on the study and regulation of objective knowledge about reality. The regulation of knowledge is expressed in laws.

Law is a philosophical category that reflects the stable, recurring connection and relationship of all events, the aspects that lead to the order of events. Knowledge of the law allows to determine the objective directions of development, to solve practical problems. Therefore, the management of the economy should be based on knowledge of the laws, their ability to apply them in practice.

General philosophical laws are expressed through categories such as matter, motion, space, time, quantity, quality, cause, effect, form, content. The laws of economic theory use the means of economic categories (property, production, demand, supply, distribution, exchange, value, price, profit, commodity, money, equilibrium).

The more fully and consistently the laws are used to manage the economy, the more efficient the labor costs will be. And, conversely, ignoring economic laws in the governance process has unintended, negative consequences for society. Therefore, the study of governance laws should include not only compliance, but also conscious application in the governance process. The conscious use of governing laws is largely related to their study. The more you study the laws, the more likely you are to apply them in practice.

However, knowledge of management laws does not guarantee their successful application in practice. It is useless to separate theory from practice in knowing the laws. This means that the use of laws depends on knowing, understanding, and applying them in a timely and correct manner. This is a crucial factor in increasing management efficiency.

- Deep and comprehensive knowledge of existing laws, taking into account the specifics of their manifestation at one stage or another;

- setting goals for economic and social development and ways to address them;

- Development of management in a market economy and the use of appropriate forms and methods.

The principles of management, in their purpose, are the fundamental basis of management theory - the link between management laws and management practices. They seem to have translated objective laws and regulations into the language of practice.

The principles of governance are both objective and subjective, which allows us to speak of the dual nature of the principle of governance. The principles of management, as the main ideas of management activity, derive directly from the laws of management and reflect the objective reality that exists independently of the human mind, that is, they are objective. At the same time, each of their principles is an idea, that is, a subjective construction, a subjective construction, which each leader performs mentally at the level of his knowledge, general and professional culture.

Management principles can achieve their goal only if the content is consistent with the objective laws of management. The main requirement for management principles is that adherence to them will increase the effectiveness of practical activities.

The author of the first principles of management is A. Fayol, a well-known French expert in the field of management theory, who stressed the need to work with the principles, not to increase or decrease them. These principles form the basis of the classical school of management.

Separation is carried out in accordance with the principles of construction and operation of the management system. These principles include:

separation of management functions and construction of management structure on their basis, integration and differentiation of functions expressed in the unity of the system of governing bodies;

-combination of operations of different management functions - functions of the governing body and the internal structure of the governing body;

- The combination of centralization and autonomy in the organization of the management structure;

- The principle of hierarchy of the control system - necessary for the distribution of information and the organization of its movement on the stages of the management system, ensuring the interaction of the upper, middle and lower levels of the management system.

Classification and concept of management function. The content of the management process is reflected in its functions. A management function is a set of different tasks aimed at solving certain management problems. Governing bodies and executors define the function of responsible management. These responsibilities are reflected in the Functional Division Regulations and Guidelines for Managers. Functional analysis of the management process forms the basis of the workload for each function, determines the number of managers, and designs the management system. Coordination is the convergence of all management functions in the joint solution of technical, economic, social issues. This will establish a link and warn you of any deviations from applicable norms and regulations.

Incentives are the activation of the human factor on the basis of broad democracy, the management of care for its interests;

Accounting and control is the control and accounting of the state of the managed system, the management of the smooth operation.

If the controlled object has specific properties, the control functions also function. However, the following functions can be distinguished in the corporate logo:

- basic production management;
- management of ancillary production;
- product quality management;
- labor and wage management, etc.

Each specific function is an integral part of the management function, which in turn is further subdivided into several parts. For example, basic production management, marketing, planning, incentives, and more. All functions are interconnected.